

Editorial: The Grand Challenges Explorations (GCE) programme

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The Grand Challenges Explorations (GCE) programme, an initiative of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, and a part of the Grand Challenges in Global Health family of programmes, was launched in 2008 as an experiment in innovation [1]. GCE casts the net wide for innovative, high-risk, high-reward ideas on a range of focused topics. To apply to GCE, applicants submit only a two-page proposal, and a blinded, champion-based review system strives to select proposals that outline a truly great idea, regardless of the background, field, or level of expertise of the applicant.

To address specific challenges facing global health and development, the GCE programme works with internal and external partners to design a set of focused challenge topics around areas where the field is stagnant or new ideas could be transformative. GCE runs two open calls for proposals per year on different topics, with open application periods each spring and fall. Topics describe specific challenges that, if met, would be transformative in their impact on global health or development. These grants of \$100,000 are designed to prove or disprove ideas quickly and gather preliminary data.

Topics are designed to address specific areas which have been traditionally under resourced and where innovation is needed. The GCE mechanism is intended to reach those both within and outside the fields of global health and development to help solve these intractable problems.

While the foundation focuses on numerous issue areas, several GCE challenge calls have sought to bring in new ideas for malaria eradication. The strategy for malaria eradication includes an emphasis on radical cure for malaria caused by either *P. falciparum* or *P. vivax*, seeking to develop liver-stage and gametocyte-targeted therapies as well as vector control methods to supplement the therapies already in the arsenal at our disposal for the fight to eradication.

Although major gains have been made toward controlling malaria in developing countries through timely interventions, diagnosis, and readily available treatments, we know our current arsenal is under-stocked. The current tools and treatments are insufficient to achieve malaria elimination in many countries, and the development of new diagnostics, next generation anti-malarial drugs, and

novel vector control methods are essential to meet this goal.

To help seek out these new ideas, GCE has tailored several topics toward malaria eradication. In the early rounds of GCE, a broad topic solicited great ideas to ‘Create New Ways to Protect Against Infectious Diseases’ (GCE Rounds 1, 2, 4 and 5), which included malaria as a priority disease [2]. Seeing the exciting ideas coming in to that topic encouraged us to focus on malaria, with a topic seeking ideas to ‘Create New Tools to Accelerate the Eradication of Malaria’ (GCE Rounds 2 and 3). Other topics also captured some great ideas for malaria eradication, including ‘Create Low-Cost Diagnostics for Priority Global Health Conditions’ (GCE Round 4) and ‘Explore New Solutions in Global Health Priority Areas’ (GCE Rounds 8 and 9).

As the GCE programme has evolved alongside the strategy to eradicate malaria, new topics have focused on the bottlenecks in the process. In two recent GCE Rounds (Round 9 and 10), a topic titled ‘New Approaches for the Interrogation of Anti-malarial Compounds’ solicited unconventional and radically new approaches, methods, and assays to analyse, characterise and prioritise anti-malarial compounds and to glean more information required for the development of next generation malaria drugs. For this unique challenge, the foundation partnered with Medicines for Malaria Venture (MMV) [3] and GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) Tres Cantos Open Lab [4] to provide anti-malarial compound collections, to researchers with innovative and unconventional approaches to assess these compounds to develop the next generation of malaria drugs. More partnerships like these, where industry, non-profit, and other sectors join forces and make their results available in the public domain to advance new technologies in the fight against malaria will keep the front lines well-stocked and pushing forward toward eradication.

Since we know innovation is essential to overcoming persistent barriers to maintaining progress against malaria, GCE will continue to tailor and evolve our calls for proposals focused on malaria eradication. And we think the evidence shows, so far, that our innovation experiment in GCE is working. We invite you to flip ahead and read a sampling of the work our GCE calls have brought in and

funded in this special edition of the *MalariaWorld Journal*. You'll find projects on unique methods for vector control, new diagnostics, and systems to support laboratory research on malaria. These represent just a few of the over 140 GCE Phase I malaria-focused grants we've made to researchers in 25 countries. Many are at the initial GCE Phase I level of \$100,000, but some have received Phase II funding of up to \$1,000,000 over two years. As we strive to define and address the major challenges facing those on the ground working toward malaria eradication, we hope to continue to see great ideas, from within and outside the malaria research community, coming forward to ensure that all people have the chance to live healthy, productive lives.

References

1. GCE webpage: <http://www.grandchallenges.org/Explorations/Pages/Introduction.aspx>
2. GCE past topics: <http://www.grandchallenges.org/Explorations/Pages/AllTopics.aspx>
3. MMV, Malaria box: <http://www.mmv.org/malariabox>
4. Tres Cantos Open Lab (GSK): <http://www.openlabfoundation.org/>

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